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The Determinations of The Consumer Credit Default Probabilities in The Telecommunication Industry

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Abstract

Risk Management subject is increasingly getting more attention especially after the 2008 global financial systems shock caused the recession, *the research* is aiming to *define* and evaluate the determinations and benefits of the statistical methods, to determine the optimum accuracy for the payments' performance, and to maximize the benefits of the financial consumer credit default swap. defining the variables that influence the risk management, applying and focusing on the telecommunications industry with the financial and non-financial dimensions, research will use *the descriptive research* method to describe, explore and investigate the amount and direction of the relationship between the variables that may affect the consumer credit defaulting, and how to prioritize it, using the multi-regression statistical analysis that explaining 34% of payments performance and transfer the rest of residual risk through financial swaps' contracts as a new suggested module for the telecommunication industry, the results support the importance for considering additional aspects for the client's profiling while taking the credit worthiness decision. recommending and encouraging further research, covering advanced techniques such as the artificial neural network "ANN" for maximum credit scoring accuracy and better payment performance. The study results avail suggestions for the telecommunication companies making adjustments for their credit risk matrix, building on the customer's profile to mitigate the defaulting risk; then research suggests hedging the remaining risk through financial tools such as the credit default swaps on lower premium fees, reaching the minimal risk level.

Keywords; Credit risk, consumer, payment performance, financial swaps contracts, telecommunication.

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1. Introduction

Begin of the 19th century companies keep searched for more advanced tools to predict and amend any factor that may lead to more relevant credit limit trust (Conant C. A. 1899). making the companies empowered to bear the bad risk of defaulters on its accepted risk level (Crook J. 1996). examining the customer profile to determine the credit safe level became ongoing interests for those who is targeting better creditworthiness (Carling K., Jacobson T., Roszbach K. 1998). during the last 25 years, banks and corporation tend to depend more on sale on the credit to increase the sales and profitability, which enforce such as those entities to revisit its policy of the credit risk mechanisms (Bureau of Census, 2000). going further the business entities increasingly developing financial tools to ensure collect more receivables, reducing debt and establish tools controlling defaulting behaviors (Council of Economic Advisers, 2000). The study will focus on collected real data sample for credit bills payments in the telecommunication industry and convenient data identifying the characteristics of the customer profile aspects and examine statistically the existence of significant between different customer profile aspects and which aspect is much more significant, suggesting a tool to the managerial level to get more close while setting the credit risk policy in the telecommunication field that is driven mainly by judgmental decision while determine the credit risk limit that leads to miss the scientific and reliable approaches to reach the maximum accuracy and benefiting from credit sales opportunities.

1.1. **Credit risk management** is playing an important role within any business and economy, the greater the competition between the companies, the greater concentration increases for the risk management and financial derivatives that mainly used for mitigating the risk and for financial hedging purpose throughout financial contracted agreements. The financial services methodologies can develop the credit risk (*Danielian, N.R. 1929*), and give wide scope for credit scoring to cover new customers' segments that traditionally missed out, such as the financial derivatives swaps that used for swapping specific risk such as the credit defaulting risk one of our focal point for this paper, we will describe and explore the benefit of the most commonly used derivatives which are the credit default swap contracts (*CDS*), used to transfer the credit defaulting risk to another financial entity with premium fees in order to hedge any predicted defaulting risk.

1.2. **The aim of the research** is to avail initial research paper to all concerned decision-makers such as risk managers, financial managers, CEOs, entrepreneur, and the regulators, focusing on the interconnected benefits for the credit scoring, customer profiling to lower the defaulting trend, and the financial credit default swap derivative to control the risk to the desired level. Swaps are one of the most beneficial derivative tools for being out of the counter (**OTC**) contracts and not restricted by the regulations standards to be the supplementary financial derivative tool beside the future contracts that already treated under the supervision of the regulator. giving more power to manage and measure financial risks, such as the collection bad debt and the default risk (*Luo, C., Wu, D., & Wu, D.,2017*) which will be the basic research focus.

1.3. **The research study exploration** is the relationship between the customer's credit payment performance and the profile elements that may impact the bad-debt, in order to reach the minimum level of defaulting risk and giving the maximum opportunities to the telecommunication companies capitalizing on the credit sales, examining the relationship will be obtained from the convenient data of Taiwan telecommunication company; this is due to the data regulations and limitations on telecommunication sector, Taiwan telecommunication data statistical module used just as a sampling proof, besides it matched the same payments systems applied within the Egyptian's telecommunication market.

Multi regression through SPSS is used to evaluate the significant relation between customer profiling like age, gender, monthly payment, total payment, tenure, and the customer churn, which will suggest adequate and dynamic credit scoring in telecommunication company as advanced applied studies recommendations based on all previous literature focusing on the consumer credit risk and this study will apply this in telecom field which did not explored enough through previous literatures, aiming minimizing the consumer credit default risks. (Hilscher, J., & Wilson, M, 2017)

2. Problem Definition

2.1. **The impact of customer profiling** on the credit default in the telecommunications industry and collecting the on-credit bills, predicting which clients are likely to pay their on credit purchase throughout scientific credit scoring machines building on the huge available data within the telecommunication companies itself for the customer profiling,

measuring the likelihood of defaulting, building a new predictive scoring model, maximizing the portfolio by determining which clients are more likely to pay, and throughout many scientific tools detecting the linear regressions for clients profile aspects and their payments performance, such as SPSS, SAS, SHAZAM, LIMDEP, SPLUS, besides suggesting the Artificial Neural Network for the researchers that need to add to this paper in the future, and the paper will apply the multi regression throughout the SPSS during the study.

Telecommunication companies need advanced statistical and scientific profiling module depending on the real significance of the customer profile such as age, sex, churn, and tenure.

2.2. **Risk mitigation** for millions of bad debts that reaches 2%~20% of total sales on credit in the telecommunication industry that could be reduced to the minimal level ever throughout applying the important financial tools (CDS) credit default swap contracts to swap the remaining bad debt risk by affordable premium fees, which attracting more researchers and encourage them to deeply study the financial benefits during the last 5 decades (Zamore, S., Ohene Djan, K., Alon, I., & Hobdari, B. 2018). In the business of debt cash flow and the decision to lay off is not the only option available in the financial business real world, through the credit default swaps the financial firms can transfer the credit risk and retains its cash flow (Parlour, Christine & Winton, Andrew. 2009)

3. Literature Review

- 3.1. **Credit scoring** is one of the main tools to select the accepted profile that has the higher probability of the good payment performance aiming the maximum profits and set apart the credit worthiness for the profile that has credit default high probability that uncovers the hidden opportunities. as the credit risk is daily occurring, there are a lot of researches discussing this topic in the banking sectors applying different approaches such as neural network besides the conventional techniques like multi regression introduce big opportunities in the credit defaulting risk forecasting, combining the judgmental technique that depend on the credit analysis's knowledge and common sense, and the credit scoring module that relies on all significant factors and giving weighted pointing structure to each single variable (A., Abdou, H., Pointon, J., & El-Masry, 2008)
- 3.2. **The literatures and researchers** have invested in the subject of credit risk in banking and financial institutions, studying the overall adoption for the credit scoring and lending approaches to scale the business productions and increasing the profits, focusing on the low-risk profiles to increase their on-credit purchase and monitoring the high risk profile to increase the credit quality (Einav, L., Jenkins, M., & Levin, J. (2013). starting by evaluation the proper classifications for customer's profile (Devasena, C. L, 2014), and how accurate credit evaluation make the balance between the risk behind the credit sales and profitability in the way that we able to predict and drive (Verbraken, T., Bravo, C., Weber, R., & Baesens, B. 2014). developing new methods for the traditional credit risk evaluations in banking sectors in order to meet the new rapid changes in the economy and the capital market (Li, Z. X, 2016), and focusing on the client's profiling while assessing its associated risks and profitability such as reputation, reason for borrowing,

personal status and spending life-style percentage out of loan/on credit purchase (Mei, X., & Jiang, Y, 2016). As credit scoring made for better financial decision making by the best use out of the historical data and statistical tools, studies confirmed that historical data has inherent noise that may impact the overall scoring evaluation, and that is one of the reasons behind the defaulting occurrences of good consumer profiles by traditional scoring, which do increase the need of combining different variables to improve the quality of the prediction (Ershadi, M. J., & Omidzadeh, D. 2018). By time the regression prediction benefits for the customers of the companies increasingly discussed through cases studies that mentioned the noticeable increase in the decision making while evaluating the credit profiles (Tripathi, D., Edla, D. R., Cheruku, R., & Kuppili, V. 2019). With much promising data in hand in the telecommunication sectors rather than the banking sectors still there is a very minimal count of research regarding the credit risk modeling in the telecommunication sectors. Literature has examined the impact of customer profile on the payment performance, one of the most significant factors to the credit risk in the banking sectors, below table is samples for the previous studies, examining the relationship payment performance and customer profile, classical determinants for the defaulting risk indicators, the result is the most of defaulter's frequency increase on earlier age, and unmarried clients default frequency is higher than married one (Vidal, M. F., & Barbon, F., 2019). Targeting the best prediction module that accurately predict the credit sales will have scheduled payments as promised in the research paper of (Djeundje, V. B., Crook, J., Calabrese, R., & Hamid, M. 2021) studied how we can predict with high accuracy the credit scoring without having a historical data for the clients such as unbanked clients extending the demographic characteristics

to the psychometric variables that it should be covered by more researches in the future building on this paper.

3.2.1 client's characteristics associated with defaulting risks based on previous studies

- Age
- Marital status
- Residence (own, rent)
- Number of years at residence
- Occupation
- Phones ownership
- Income
- Years in current job
- Previous employment
- Years in previous job
- Number of dependents
- Credit history
- Account ownership
- Credit outstanding
- Outstanding debts
- Credit purpose

3.3. **The benefit of the prediction**, and exploring the artificial neural network (ANN) as one of prediction modeling that could be optimized in the credit default and payment performance prediction, depending and considering all customer's profiling aspects and as an advanced level getting more benefits out of the ongoing machine learning adjustments that leads by time to the optimal prediction outcomes, currently we have promising opportunity in the telecommunication sector in Egypt to apply such as this revolutionary module or even start to adapt the current used credit worthiness modeling, saving time and cost throughout combining the ANN prediction module with the credit officers efforts to reduce the judgement errors. (Moula, F. E., Guotai, C., & Abedin, 2017)

3.4. **Stable and reliable creditworthiness modeling** is a crucial for all sectors' management to help in managing the credit default risk probability, depending on multivariate aspects it needs for a dynamic scoring module that gets adjusted building on multidimensional aspects, considering the customer demographic profile besides the financial credit behavior, and the credit characteristics (Baklouti, I., & Bouri, A., 2014).

4. **Research Methodology & Design**

4.1. **The non-contrived variables** and a minimal amount of controlled data, we have successfully obtained a real convenient sample from a telecommunication filled study, data is a cross-sectional study, data covering different customer profiles during 2019.

4.2. **The proactive risk management** is the research goal to create the credit scoring model that able to mitigate the risk, throughout exploring the correlation of customer profiling, credit scoring, and the collection of bad-debt ratios at the same time controlling the residual risk throughout swapping the default risk of collecting the debt and availing more resilient hedging tools building on a statistical model based on all the historical data to improve the accuracy while determining the credit decision avoiding personal judgment and being more cost-efficient.

4.3. **The research questions** can be summarized into the below question

What are the significant factors that affect the defaulting level?

4.4. **Research data sources**

the data will be obtained from similar telecommunications industries, the world bank database, and the central agency for public mobilization and statistics Research is using

quantitative and qualitative variables to measure the relationship. The study by design focusing on the data of the Taiwan telecommunication company due to data regulations in Egypt, knowing that the outcomes has been evaluated and it is almost similar outcomes

5. Research importance

- 5.1. **Scientific credit scoring module:** Saving millions of the yearly bad-debt in the telecommunication industry, developing the credit risk previous studies on the banking credit filed to be applied on the telecommunication sector, exploring the benefits that financial derivatives deliver to the market as a resilient risk management tool.
- 5.2. **The credit default swap contracts in the telecommunication** industry as a field study, which empowers the markets by multidimensional risk management hedging tool, effectively managing a sustainable business on low cost and risk, and for coherent business continuity. (Hilscher, J., & Wilson, M. (2017))

6. Research objectives

- 6.1.1. **Explore the safe use of the credit score mechanism** avoiding the defaulter's behaviors and recommend financial tools to control the default risk more through credit default swaps contract (**CDS**) throughout multidimensional variables, in the telecommunications industry.
- 6.1.2. **Multi Regression applications in telecommunication sector** throughout SPSS statistical Multiple regression analysis analyze the relationship between Credit

Default Risk Score as a single dependent variable and the several independent variables.

6.2. **Scientific credit scoring and common sense** decrease the defaulting risk when it combines rather than depending on credit analysis judgments only

7. The Analysis Variables

Variables	
Dependent	Credit Default Risk Score
Independent	Gender
	Age
	Partner
	Dependents
	tenure
	Monthly Charges
	Total Charges
	Churned

8.The Module Framework

8.1.1. **The variables affect the credit default** and most of the important variables that describe the correlation with the defaulting level translated into payment scoring with weighted average for each variable based on its significance that results eventually an automated credit default risk score model that indicates the clients that most likely will pay {0/defaulters 1/non-defaulter}

The module framework Diagram, Figure 2

** The study did not find interrelationships between independent variables*

9. Research hypothesis

Based on the previous literature review and the statistical regression analysis

H_0 – There is a significant relationship between customer profiling and Credit Default Risk Score.

H_a – *Developing the Credit Default Risk Score, considering profile characteristics, increase the on-credit sales collection probability.*

10. Data Analysis and Testing Hypotheses.

10.1.1. The statistical data used the multi-regression statistical analysis to predict and examine the correlation between the independent and dependent variables,

throughout classifying the population into {0/defaulters or 1/non-defaulters} collection for each item in the sample, then measure the independent variable mean, standard deviation, Z-score, confidence interval and the regressions for each item while all affected items considered, besides measuring the interrelationship between the independent items with no correlation between independents itself.

10.1.2. **The correlation result** is highly coefficient for age, gender, marital status and there is relationship between the Credit Default Risk Score and the multi variables that explain 16.7% of the changes in payment behavior score

10.2. **Testing H1:** there is a relation between the consumer payment behavior and variable profiling {Gender, Senior Citizen, Partner, Dependents, Tenure, Monthly Charges, Total charges, and Churned}

10.3. **Testing H2:** independent variable consideration will develop more predictable payment scoring and sales volume

The b-coefficients dictate our regression model

$$\text{Credit Default Risk Score}' = 2.431 - (0.153 \text{ Age}) - (0.069 \text{ Dependents}) - (0.012 \text{ tenure}) + (0.160 \text{ Churned})$$

11. Results.

11.1. The Defaulting Probability: the multi regression analysis indicates that customer profiling is explaining 34% of payment behavior, that support controlling the bad debt ratios that its average accepted level in the companies “2% out of the sales on credit”, that support the companies’ strategy to maintain the receivables ratios and profitability.

11.2. The most significant demographic defaulting factors is Age, marital status, tenure, and churn ratios has the most significant correlation with the defaulting behavior that explains, high default frequency of early age, single and new clients, besides the low satisfaction level that may lead to increase the churn and settling the credited bills, losing a good customer profile from the population

12. Findings and Analysis

12.1. Demographic data

In this part, the researcher has calculated the frequencies and percentages of the demographic data.

Table (): summary statistics for demographic data

Variables	categories	Frequency	Percent
gender	male	3555	50.5
	female	3488	49.5
Senior Citizen	junior	5901	83.8
	senior	1142	16.2
Partner	single	3641	51.7
	partner	3402	48.3
Dependents	independent	4933	70.0
	dependent	2110	30.0
Phone Service	has mobile	6361	90.3
	no mobile	682	9.7
Total		7043	100.0

According to the previous table it is notable that, 50.5% of the sample respondents are males, 83.8% of the respondents are juniors, 51.7% of the respondents are singles, 70% of the respondents are independents, 90.3% of the respondents have mobile.

12.2. Study variables

In this part, the researcher has calculated the frequencies and percentages of some of data variables

Table (): Descriptive statistics for study variables

Variables	no	yes	no internet ser
	Frequency		
	Percent %		
Multiple Lines	3390	2971	682
	48.1	42.2	9.7
Internet Service	3096	2421	1526
	44.0	34.4	21.7
Online Security	3498	2019	1526
	49.7	28.7	21.7
Online Backup	3088	2429	1526
	43.8	34.5	21.7
Device Protection	3095	2422	1526
	43.9	34.4	21.7
TechSupport	3473	2044	1526
	49.3	29.0	21.7
Streaming TV	2810	2707	1526
	39.9	38.4	21.7
Streaming Movies	2785	2732	1526
	39.5	38.8	21.7

According to the previous table it is notable that, 42.2% of the respondents ensure that there are multiple lines, 34.4% of the respondents ensure that there are internet service, 28.7% of the respondents ensure that there are online security, 34.5% of the respondents ensure that there are online backup, 34.4% of the respondents ensure that there are device protection, 29.0% of the respondents ensure that there are techsupport, 38.4% of the respondents ensure that there are streaming tv, 38.8% of the respondents ensure that there are streaming movies,

Table (): Cont. descriptive statistics for study variables

Variables	categories	Frequency	Percent
Contract	month	3875	55.0
	2 years	1695	24.1
	year	1473	20.9
PaperlessBilling	paperless	4171	59.2
	paper	2872	40.8
PaymentMethod	electronic check	2365	33.6
	maile check	1612	22.9
	bank transter (automatic)	1544	21.9
	credit card (automatic)	1522	21.6
Churn	churn	5174	73.5

	didnt churn	1869	26.5
Payment Quality	yes	5523	78.4
	no	1520	21.6
Total		7043	100.0

Table (): Cont. descriptive statistics for study variables

Variables	Obs	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Devia
tenure [Month/s	704	0	72	32.37	24.559
MonthlyCharge	704	18.25	118.75	64.7617	30.0900
TotalCharges	703	18.80	8684.80	2283.300	2266.77

According to the previous table it is notable that, the mean of tenure is 32.37, while the standard deviation is 24.559, the mean of Monthly Charges is 64.7617, while the standard deviation is 30.09005, the mean of Total Charges is 2283.3004, while the standard deviation is 2266.77

1. Regression model

In this part, the researcher has conducted simple linear regression. F-test was used for checking the significance of the model, the model is significant when p-value < 0.05.

T-test was used for checking the significance of independent variables, the independent variable has significant effect when p-value > 0.05. R-square was used for determining “to what extent the independent variables managed to explain variation in the dependent variables.

Table (): Regression model

	B	Std. Error	t	Sig.
Intercept	0.5497	0.0166	33.2070	1E-224
gender	0.0003	0.0056	0.0521	1E+00
Senior Citizen	-0.0027	0.0081	-0.3387	7E-01
Partner	0.0209	0.0067	3.1148	2E-03
Dependents	-0.0024	0.0071	-0.3299	7E-01
tenure	0.0037	0.0003	12.6469	3E-36
Phone Service	0.0044	0.0103	0.4306	7E-01
Multiple Lines	0.0029	0.0008	3.8428	1E-04
Internet Service	-0.0015	0.0011	-1.3285	2E-01
Contract	-0.0092	0.0009	-10.4915	1E-25
Monthly Charge	0.0006	0.0002	2.5341	1E-02
Total Charges	0.0000	0.0000	-2.4307	2E-02
Churn	0.3067	0.0073	41.9680	0E+00
F	302.126			
Sig.	.000 ^b			
R Square	0.340			

According to the previous table it is notable that,

- The model is significant as the independent variable affect the dependent variable and $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$
- The independent variable managed to explain 34% of the variations in the dependent variable, where $R\text{ Square} = 0.340$
- There is significant positive effect for gender the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = 0.0003$, any increasing in gender by unit, the " the dependent variable " will increase by 0.0003 units. There is significant positive effect for Partner the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = 0.0209$, any increasing in Partner by unit, the " the dependent variable " will increase by 0.0209 units. There is significant positive effect for tenure the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = 0.0037$, any increasing in tenure by unit, the " the dependent variable " will increase by 0.0037 units. There is significant positive effect for Churn the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = 0.3067$, any increasing in Churn by unit, the " the dependent variable " will increase by 0.3067 units.
- There is significant negative effect for Senior Citizen the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = -0.0027$, any increasing in Senior Citizen by unit, the "the dependent variable " will decrease by 0.0027 units. There is significant negative effect for Dependents the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = -0.0024$, any increasing in Dependents by unit, the "the dependent variable " will decrease by 0.002427 units. There is significant negative effect for Internet Service the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = -0.0015$, any increasing in Internet Service by unit, the "the dependent variable " will decrease by 0.0015 units. There is significant negative effect for Contract the on "the dependent variable", where $p\text{-value} = 0.0001 < 0.05$. $B = -0.0092$, any increasing in Contract by unit, the "the dependent variable " will decrease by 0.0092 units.

13. Discussion

The research paper results support the hypotheses, after evaluating the payment performance for 7000 different clients in the Taiwan telecommunication company during two years, that used just as a statistical proof, the findings show that the clients' demographic factors affecting the defaulting probability, The demographic factors correlated with the payment performance and the credit default probability, it finds that the consideration of the clients demographic aspects is a must to correctly decide the right profile that most likely will pay. There is no significant interaction relationship found between the demographic aspects itself for the same client. Male on earlier age and single were significantly correlated with the defaulting probability considering the churn and tenure aspects. Reference to previous study done by (A. E. Masry, 2008) Appendix 2.1. it found that considering the personnel profiling while evaluating the credit scoring structure besides applying new advanced statically techniques such as the artificial neural network ANN as advanced level comparing the regression statistical gives significant correlated results and reducing the likelihood of the defaulters, which support the research proposal. that was consistent with the relevant study done by (Baklouti, I., & Bouri, A., 2014) Appendix 2.2 Focusing on the statistical evidence for the credit score predictions, building on the financial and the demographic aspect, and supports that including the demographic aspects leads to more accurate evaluation for the microloans payments performance. In a recent study by (Moula, F. E., Guotai, C., & Abedin, M. Z., 2017). Proved and urged for more academic studies to cover the gap found in the credit default scoring modules that causing many shortfalls and gaps to predict the client's payments performance building on the statistical modulating that able to integrate all profiling aspects. In another study by (Crook, J. N., Edelman, D. B., & Thomas, L. C., 2007) it demonstrates the promising research opportunities for the profitable scoring statistical module that increase the accuracy of the credit application

assessment and applying the banking policies and regulations which support the research's subsequence. the study hypotheses supported more by (Brown, K., & Moles, P.,2014). indicating the importance for evaluating the exact profiling aspects has a significant correlation with the defaulting probability and depending on the statistical determinations, involve the experience and knowledge with the range of analytics tools. Evaluating the credit profiling module comparing after and before the financial crisis supports the importance for the ongoing evaluation for financial and social aspects to reach accurate credit scoring (Sandica, A. M., & Dudian, M.,2020). Appendix 2.3. advancing the benefits of the scientific and statistical approaches while applying the credit scoring evaluation to reach the minimal risk, the study of (Luo, C., Wu, D., & Wu, D., 2017). Indicate that the deep machine learning empowerment able to avail accurate credit scoring applicable and complementary for the credit default swap, dealing with complicated assessment financial and demographic information.

It is beyond this research proposal the application of the artificial neural network ANN as a dynamic credit scoring evaluation and the research highly recommend further efforts for the credit default scoring including all correlated aspects into the artificial neural network ANN in the future building on this research results.

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Appendix

1.1. The below tables summarize the descriptive statistical of the study variable

Variable	Unit	Comment		
Payment Score	0, 1	0 = default/bad credit	1 = Paid/good credit	
Gender	0, 1	1 = Female	0 = Male	
Senior Citizen	0, 1	1 = Senior	0 = Junior	
Partner	0, 1	0 = Single	1 = Partner	
Dependents	0, 1	0 = depended	1 = independent	
tenure	month	Tenure in month/s		
PhoneService	0, 1	0 = no mobile	1 = has mobile	
MultipleLines	0, 1, 10	0 = no mobile	1 = one mobile	10 = has more 1 line
InternetService	0, 1, 10	0 = no ADSL	1 = DSL	10 = Fiber
Contract	0, 1, 10	0 = month	1 = year	10 = 2 years
PaperlessBilling	0, 1	0 = paper	1 = paperless	
MonthlyCharges	amount	amount in dollar		
TotalCharges	amount	amount in dollar		
Churn	0, 1	0 = churn	1 = didn't churn	

Regression Statistics

Multiple R	0.583307381
R Square	0.340247501
Adjusted R Square	0.339121323
Standard Error	0.233512485
Observations	7043

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	12	197.6921555	16.47434629	302.1259149	0
Residual	7030	383.3324079	0.054528081		
Total	7042	581.0245634			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Intercept	0.549669743	0.016552833	33.2069887	9.638E-225
gender	0.000289947	0.005567254	0.052080785	0.958465803
SeniorCitizen	-0.00272972	0.008059515	-0.338695279	0.734849413
Partner	0.020949289	0.006725731	3.11479722	0.00184812
Dependents	-0.002350515	0.007125694	-0.329864647	0.741512066
tenure	0.003744889	0.000296111	12.64690824	2.88336E-36
PhoneService	0.004429714	0.010287508	0.430591552	0.666778585
MultipleLines	0.002927176	0.000761727	3.842812843	0.000122704
InternetService	-0.001526109	0.001148777	-1.328464195	0.184067926
Contract	-0.009246567	0.000881342	-10.4914571	1.45964E-25
MonthlyCharges	0.000617652	0.000243738	2.534081153	0.011295789
TotalCharges	-9.39344E-06	3.86444E-06	-2.430734059	0.015093111
Churn	0.306656622	0.007306914	41.96800563	0

Above average shows

1. The module is translating 33.9% of the payments scoring
2. Partner, Tenure, Multiline, contract duration, charges monthly/total and churn have the peak coefficient correlation

2. Previous Studies statistical references

- 2.1. Abdou, H., J. Pointon and A. E. Masry (2008), Neural Nets Versus Conventional Techniques in Credit Scoring in Egyptian Banking. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 35(3), pp. 1289.

Appendix A. List of variables used in building the proposed credit scoring models

Variable/description	Code	Unit	Comment
X_1 Loan amount*	LOAN AMO	No.	–
X_2 Loan duration	–	–	Loan duration is 4 years in all cases in this sample.
X_3 Company*	COMP	10, 01, 00	10 = Public sector, 01 = Local private sector, 00 = Multinational company.
X_4 Branch	–	–	The bank has a branch to serve and collect instalments (i.e., clients work or live in a very remote area that there is no branch in the city).
X_5 Sex*	SEX	0, 1	0 = Male, 1 = Female
X_6 Marital status*	MAR STA	0, 1	0 = Married, 1 = Single
X_7 Age*	AGE	Years	Clients ages from 25 to 59 years.
X_8 Monthly salary*	SALA	No.	–
X_9 Additional income*	ADD INC	0, 1	0 = N/A, 1 = Suitable
X_{10} House owned or rented*	HOR	0, 1	0 = Rented, 1 = Owned
X_{11} House rent > loan tenure	–	–	The client must have a rent contract for 4 years or higher to be greater than loan tenure (4 years).
X_{12} Home telephone*	TELE	0, 1	0 = N/A, 1 = Ok confirmed (land line).
X_{13} Utility bill	–	–	Clients must have a utility bill not less than 6 months.
X_{14} Title/position	–	–	It means the occupation of customers: workers is less grade than white collar, workers are not accepted.
X_{15} Education level*	EDU	0, 1	0 = University, 1 = Higher education 100% university or higher, it is a must.
X_{16} Loans from other banks*	LFOB	0, 1	0 = N/A, 1 = Nil
X_{17} Relation with other banks	–	–	Through an investigation report from the central bank of Egypt (provides the client's history).
X_{18} Credit card status	–	–	All clients have valid credit card(s).
X_{19} Corporate guarantee*	COR GUAR	0, 1	0 = No, 1 = Ok from creditable company. There is no such a default with a client has a corporate guarantee.
X_{20} Other guarantors	–	–	If required.
Y Loan quality* (dependent variable)	LOAN QUA	0, 1	0 = Default/bad credit, 1 = Paid/good credit

* Variables finally selected in the credit scoring models.

Appendix B. Statistical analysis for conventional models

Discriminating function for DA model:					Discriminating function for DA ₁ model:				
Functions derived	Wilks Lambda	Chi-Square	DF	P-Value	Functions derived	Wilks Lambda	Chi-Square	DF	P-Value
1	0.543615	349.2512	12	0.0000	1	0.5438	349.9703	9	0.0000
Analysis of deviance and likelihood ratio tests for PA model:					Analysis of deviance and likelihood ratio tests for PA ₁ model:				
Analysis of deviance					Analysis of deviance				
Source	Deviance	Df	P-Value		Source	Deviance	Df	P-Value	
Model	374.5	13	0.0000		Model	370.674	9	0.0000	
Residual	284.906	567	1.0000		Residual	288.732	571	1.0000	
Total (corr.)	659.407	580			Total (corr.)	659.407	580		
Likelihood ratio tests					Likelihood ratio tests				
Factor	Chi-square	Df	P-Value		Factor	Chi-square	Df	P-Value	
ADD INC	0.00152616	1	0.9688		AGE	10.8605	1	0.0010	
AGE	12.0717	1	0.0005		COR GUAR	72.5957	1	0.0000	
COR GUAR	72.313	1	0.0000		EDU	10.7326	1	0.0011	
EDU	11.6285	1	0.0006		HOR	5.60935	1	0.0179	
HOR	2.70153	1	0.1002		LFOB	69.6341	1	0.0000	
LFOB	72.0333	1	0.0000		LOAN AMO	99.0516	1	0.0000	
LOAN AMO	78.0624	1	0.0000		MAR STA	6.08719	1	0.0136	
MAR STA	5.04102	1	0.0248		SALA	5.84293	1	0.0156	
SALA	5.69163	1	0.0170		TELE	61.5081	1	0.0000	
SEX	0.53373	1	0.4650						
TELE	61.4374	1	0.0000						
COMP	3.49304	2	0.1744						

2.2. Can credit-scoring models effectively predict microloans default? Statistical evidence from the Tunisian microfinance bank

2.2.1. Baklouti, I., & Bouri, A. (2014). Can credit-scoring models effectively predict microloans default? Statistical evidence from the Tunisian microfinance bank. World Scientific Book Chapters, 57-69.

Table 1. Variables overview.

Variable	Variable Description
Borrower-Demographic Variables	
X_1 = Borrower's age	≤ 23 (X_{11}), 24–25 (X_{12}), 26–34 (X_{13}), 35–40 (X_{14}), 41–45 (X_{15}), >45 (X_{16})
X_2 = Borrower's gender	Male (X_{21}), female (X_{22})
X_3 = Marital status	Single (X_{31}), married (X_{32})
X_4 = Educational level	Low educational level (X_{41}), graduate and higher educational level (X_{42})
X_5 = Job experience (in years)	<2 (X_{51}), 2–4 (X_{52}), 4–7 (X_{53}), > 7 (X_{54})
Loan-Characteristic Variables	
X_6 = Credit amount	≤ 1935 (X_{61}), [1936, 2399] (X_{62}), [2400, 3598] (X_{63}), [3599, 4349] (X_{64}), [4350, 4998] (X_{65}), [4999, 5918] (X_{66}), [5919, 8832] (X_{67}), >8832 (X_{68})
X_7 = Credit purpose	Business creation (X_{71}), business extension (X_{72})
X_8 = Business sector	Agriculture (X_{81}), services (X_{82}), artisanal (X_{83}), small trades (X_{84})
Credit-Behavioral Variables	
X_9 = Number of previous loans	Two loans (X_{91}), one loan (X_{92}), new customer (X_{93})
X_{10} = Previous loans default	New customer (X_{101}), all credits paid back duly (X_{102}), delay in paying off in the past (X_{103})

Table 2. Descriptive statistics.

Variable	Value	Percentages (%)	Default Frequency (%)
Borrower's age	≤23	11.8	33.2
	24–25	8.2	40.4
	26–34	40.5	46.0
	35–40	20	41.5
	41–45	9.8	32.2
	>45	9.7	24.3
Borrower's gender	Male	75.1	38.8
	Female	24.9	42.5
Marital status	Single	51.8	44.1
	Married	48.2	34.9
Educational level	Lower educational level	87.9	35.2
	Graduate and higher educational level	12.1	72.0
Professional experience	<2 year	5.2	55.7
	2–4 years	25.9	44.3
	4–7 years	20.7	39.6
	>7 years	48.2	35.5
Credit amount	≤1935	10	62.9
	[1936,2399]	9.2	48.3
	[2400,3598]	20.8	48.4
	[3599,4349]	10.1	37.0
	[4350,4998]	10	28.0
	[4999,5918]	10	44.0
	[5919,8832]	19.9	16.2
	>8832	10.1	47.2
Credit purpose	Business Creation	80.9	39.7
	Business Extension	19.1	39.6
Business sector	Agriculture	16.6	1.2
	Services	33.2	46.4
	Artisanal	3.3	41.5
	Small Trades	46.9	48.4
Number of previous loans	One loan	91.7	38.9
	Two loans	7.3	48.9
	New customer	1	46.2
Previous loan defaults	New customer	94.7	39.0
	All credits paid back duly	4.6	50.2
	Payment delay in paying off in the past	0.7	63.9

2.3. Sandica, A. M., & Dudian, M. (2020). Determinants of Consumer Credit Default in Romania: A Comparison of Machine Learning Algorithms. In Social Credit Rating (pp. 657-674). Springer Gabler, Wiesbaden

2.3.1.1. The defaulter profiles after and before the financial crisis

